

Innovative Strategies for Improving the Teaching of Entrepreneurship Development Education in Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana

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This study examined the innovative strategies for improving the teaching of entrepreneurship development education in Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana. The study specifically examined the relationship of: business plan development instructional strategy, industrial collaboration instructional strategy that will improve the teaching of entrepreneurship development education in the Nigerian tertiary institutions. Data for the study were sourced from primary data using questionnaire and interview. Hypotheses raised were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC), result of the hypotheses shows that business plan development instructional strategy will positively and significantly improve teaching of entrepreneurship development education in Nigeria with Pearson Correlation result of .723** and P value of 0.000. This implies that business plan development instructional strategy has a positive influence on the teaching of entrepreneurship development education in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria. It was discovered from the study that industrial collaboration instructional strategy can improved teaching of entrepreneurship development education has a positive influence on the teaching of entrepreneurship development education in the Nigeria with Pearson Correlation result of .967** and P value of 0.000. This implies that industrial collaboration instructional strategy has a positive influence on improved teaching of entrepreneurship development education in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

Keywords: Innovative Strategies; Entrepreneurship Development Education; Tertiary Institutions; Teaching and Assessment Methods; Self-Employed Graduates

Introduction

Due to an increased rate of unemployment phenomenon among the world community members, entrepreneurship education (EE) is considered as a tool for promoting self-employment to graduates of tertiary education including those graduating from higher learning education (HLE) (Gyamfi, 2014; Kalimasi, 2014; Mangasini, 2015; Peter, & Rankhumise, 2012). In addition, the World Entrepreneurship Investment Forum (WIEF) held in 2017 in Manama, Bahrain, agreed that the knowledge of entrepreneurship should promote domestic investment, thus leading to job creation in the context of the current challenges and opportunities associated with the fourth industrial revolution era (WIEF, 2019). However, things are different as some of the studies indicate that the majority of graduates, Nigeria in particular, experience failure to start-up their own business ventures despite having graduated from different institutions teaching EE (Ghisina, 2014; Lekeko, Peter & Rankhumise, 2012). In the current study, a graduate is referred to as any individual person graduated from the higher learning institution offering business studies including EE. Recently, the body of literature indicates that there is a significant relationship between EE and the success of entrepreneurs (Bawuah, Buame, & Hinson, 2006; Lonappan & Devaraj, 2011; Zhou & Xu, 2012; Fatoki, 2014). This being the case, EE is considered as the study of sources of business opportunities, deals with how to discover, exploit and evaluate them for business start-up (Fatoki, 2014). Furthermore, EE is an essential strategy for creating future goods or services (Qian & Lai, 2012; Muñoz, Salinero, Peña, & Sanchez de Pablo, 2019). As a result, all over the world, EE is taught in colleges and universities either as a full programme or a part of business-related programmes (Arasti, Kiani, & Imanipour, 2013; Ghisina, 2014; Kalimasi, 2014).

In the United States of America, for instance, EE started to be taught in higher learning education (HLE) earlier than other countries in the 1940s, and up to the 2000s, there were more than 1600 learning institutions with EE related courses (Zhou & Xu, 2012). Other countries from different continents in Europe, Australia, Asia, and Africa followed later. For example, in Canada, serious teaching of EE started in the 1970s while in Germany, China, and India it started in the 1990s (Zhou & Xu, 2012). In India, EE started with nine pilot colleges as the government's strategy to expand employment, and up to 2013, there were about 100 departments dealing with EE (Pradhan & Sahoo, 2013). In Africa, most of HLE introduced EE in the 2000s (Bawuah, Buame, & Hinson, 2006). For example, the University of Ghana introduced EE as a compulsory course for all freshers entering into university in the academic year 2015 (Bawuah et al., 2006).

In Nigeria, the decision to integrate EE in HLE is linked to the National Higher Education and Training Policy (FRN, 2014), and the Small and Medium Enterprise Development Policy (URT, 2003). Both policies, consider mainstreaming entrepreneurship in the education sector as a deliberate effort to expand employment opportunities, thus, reducing the rate of unemployment to graduates after their school lives. The intervention of mainstreaming entrepreneurship education in higher learning education system aimed at promoting the spirit of graduates of HLE to become entrepreneurs, making education system to be a job creator, and coping with those changes associated with science and technology (Olomi & Sabokwigina, 2010). As a result, recently, most higher learning institutions in Nigeria have been offering various courses related EE so as to respond to the national strategy of eradicating unemployment phenomenon (Kalimasi, 2014; Olomi & Sabokwigina, 2010). However, ineffective models and methods used in preparing students to become entrepreneurs are the key identified obstacles to the quality of EE provided in Nigeria. The use of traditional methods of teaching such as normal lectures and written based form of assessments, are sources of graduates' failure to start-up their own business since such forms of methods do not focus on promoting creativity and innovation that are essential components for someone to become an entrepreneur (Fulgence, 2015; Kalimasi & Herman, 2016; Olomi & Sabokwigina, 2010). Furthermore, it has been argued that those traditional approaches of teaching EE, instead of preparing students to become entrepreneurs, are preparing them to be employees of other entrepreneurs (Fayomi, et al., 2019). Consequently, based on the weaknesses of those teaching methods, unemployment as a critical phenomenon in Nigeria has been increasing rapidly instead of decreasing with the increase in number of graduates (Kalimasi, 2014). Education is not a preparation for life, education is life itself. It is a vital instrument of change in any society (Amarachi, 2023). Education according to Oduma (2020) is a tool for nation building. The development of a country's natural resources is dependent on the quality of its human resources and the quality of human resources in turn depends on education. Education contributes to the individual's personal development, increases his/her productivity and income at work and facilitates participation in economic and social life.

Ekanem (2019) noted that, for education to prepare its recipients for life; it must: Provide men and women with the minimum of skills needed to take their place in the society and to seek further knowledge, provide men and women with vocational training that will enable them to be self-reliance through entrepreneurship, awoken an interest in taste for knowledge and Equip individual(s) with critical thinking and problem solving.

Obayi (2020) expressed that formal education system in the recent past seem to be continuously turning graduates who are ill-prepared to help in the development of the society. It is a process of preparing people for non-existent jobs. It might equally be worthwhile to note that education is variously qualified. People talk of qualitative, functional and useful education. If these qualifications are anything to go by, it follows that entrepreneurial education is one of the ways to positive change in the society.

Odah and Ayo (2022) see entrepreneurship education as enterprise education. Thus, they defined enterprise education as learning directed towards developing in young people those skills, competencies, understanding and attributes which equip them to be innovative, and to identify, create, initiate and successfully manage personal business and work opportunities including working for others. Education is not all about preparing someone on how to run a business, but also encouraging creative thinking and promoting a strong sense of self-worth and accountability. Through entrepreneurship education students learn how to create a business opportunity, the knowledge created through entrepreneurship education includes: ability to recognize business opportunities in one's life, ability to create and operate a new venture, ability to think in a creative and critical manner.

Statement of the Problem

It is argued that the need for effective teaching of EE is of paramount importance to enhance self-employment among the graduates of HLE whose number tends to increase very fast in Nigeria (Fulgence, 2015). However, despite several years of investing EE in Nigeria HLE, still a large portion of graduates are incompetent, hence, they cannot start-up their own business ventures (Fulgence, 2015; Kalimasi 2014). Added to this problem is the issue of poverty and idleness among graduates. To arrest this situation, the Federal Government of Nigeria recently embarked on education revitalization aimed at making the system more functional and relevant to both the beneficiaries and the entire society. The reform agenda equally aims at introducing new changes or replacing all ineffective practices of the education system with new practices validated by research as effective. Ofem and Mebala (2021) reported a survey carried out by NUC in 2010 revealed that university education in Nigeria, does not adequately prepare graduates to be self-reliant. In this direction, Akpan (2019) expressed that it is the task of tertiary institutions to devise the best approach to make their graduates innovative and creative in visualizing business opportunities and exploiting same using their skills and entrepreneurial knowledge. It is a general believe in this direction, that if graduates are properly prepared or groomed with entrepreneurship development education, they will be in a better option to overcome poverty, generate employment for themselves and create wealth essential for their living, and contribute significantly to the economic and social development to their immediate community or environment.

To ensure immediate approach to meeting this condition, the FGN has made the teaching of entrepreneurship education compulsory across all levels of education (FRN, 2014). In spite of the fact that entrepreneurship development education is presently taught across all levels of education as reported by Umeh (2019), Nnadi (2020) and Mebala (2021) respectively noted that one of the major causes of unemployment and idleness among graduates is that entrepreneurship development education is not being taught well in our tertiary institutions. Lecturers and skills facilitators failed to use innovative instructional strategies to impart desirable knowledge, skills and competences that will help to establish and manage a profit-oriented business or effectively managed someone's business intrapreneur(s).

Therefore, it is against this background, the study is aimed at filling the gap in the literature by exploring effective EE teaching methods and assessment procedures for self-employment among the graduates of higher learning education.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to identify the innovative strategies for improving the teaching of entrepreneurship development education in Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana. Specifically, the study intends to:

- I. Identify how business plan development instructional strategy would improve the teaching of entrepreneurship development education.
- II. Identify how industrial collaboration instructional strategy would improve the teaching of entrepreneurship development education.

Statement of the Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are formulated for the study:

- I. Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between business plan development instructional strategy and improved teaching of entrepreneurship development education.
- II. Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between industrial collaboration instructional strategy and industrial collaboration instructional strategy

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Meaning of an Entrepreneur and Entrepreneurship

An entrepreneur is an individual who renovates a business which did not exist before (Qian & Lai, 2012). It is also considered as an individual who discovers, evaluates, and exploits opportunities to create future goods or services (Muñoz, Salinero, Peña, & Sanchez de Pablo, 2019). On the other side, entrepreneurship as an activity is done by an entrepreneur which involves four main components namely as vision, innovation, risk taking, and organizing the business (Mohammed, 2018). It is an ability to foresee and start a new business venture by using the learned knowledge and experiences from the environment to manage the business despite the available challenges which might face the business (Fatoki, 2014). In the current study, we have defined an entrepreneur as any person who has started up his or her own business venture (s) after graduating with EE from the college or university.

Teaching of EE

Currently, there have been various suggestions among scholars about how EE can be taught for effective learning. While some scholars try to direct about which kinds of teaching methods suit EE (Arasti, Kiani, & Imanipour, 2013; Lonappan & Devaraj, 2011), others suggest conditions guiding the decision to select a particular method for EE (Pradhan & Sahoo, 2013). For example, according to Lonappan & Devaraj (2011), methods such as project, lecture, report writing, discussion, individual presentation, guest speaker, video recording, web-based and seminar, are more appropriate to EE. In addition to that, Arasti, Kiani, & Imanipour (2013) view that while students are taught about business planning, the use of case studies and lectures are more appropriate. Henry et al. (2006) suggest that there should be a variety of methods to teach EE varying from lecture presentations, handouts, group discussions, case studies and role plays. According to the European Union, the use of learning by doing, digital tools, internship, interacting with entrepreneurs, multimedia, mentoring, and experiment are highly recommended for EE teaching (Fayomi, et al., 2019).

However, the second group of scholars do not mention methods to be used while teaching EE, instead, they suggest guiding situations for the selection of EE teaching methods. For example, Pradhan & Sahoo (2013) argue that there is no specific method to teach EE but the selection of approaches should consider the relationship among four important components of EE. The components are programme goals, audience, content and assessment. Likewise, Arasti, Kiani, & Imanipour (2013) suggest that the course objective of EE should guide on how to teach students. In the same line with suggesting guiding conditions for method selection, Fayomi, et al. (2019) argue that key determinants to EE teaching are who teaches, content to be taught and the place where learning is taking place.

Therefore, based on the above-reviewed literature on how to teach EE, one would identify two categories of teaching methods and assessment procedures which are either in traditional or action-based methods. According to Arasti, Kiani & Imanipour (2013), the use of traditional methods such as normal lectures, make a student passive, and thus cannot prepare him or her to work as an independent entrepreneur, instead, these methods prepare a student to work with entrepreneurs (employees of other entrepreneurs). On the other side, it is highly recommended that action-based methods should be used to teach EE. According to Pradhan & Sahoo (2013), action-based methods refer to those teaching approaches characterized by learning by doing, involvement in the real-life situation or more didactical and conventional procedures whose efficiency can be assessed. Examples of action-based methods are role-plays, case studies, project work, simulation, games, and so forth.

Teaching Methods in Entrepreneurship Education

Lonappan et al (2011) classify the teaching methods into following categories: case Study, group discussion, individual presentation, individual written report, group project, formal lectures, guest speakers, action learning, seminar, web-based learning, video recorded.

The study by Solomon et al (2002) highlighted that the most popular teaching methods in entrepreneurship education are creation of business plans, case studies and lectures. However, Hytti and O’Gorman (2004) suggest different view as they argued that there are many ways to offer entrepreneurship education, depending on the objectives of such education. If the objective of the education is to increase the understanding of what entrepreneurship is about, the most effective way to accomplish the objective is to provide information through public channels such as media, seminars, or lectures. These methods are effective in terms of sending the relevant information to a broader population in a relative short time period. If the objective is to equip individuals with entrepreneurial skills, which are applicable directly to work, the best way is to provide education and training that enable individuals to involve directly in the entrepreneurial process, such as industrial training. Lastly, if the objective of the education is to prepare individuals to act as entrepreneurs, the most effective technique is to facilitate experiments by trying entrepreneurship out in a controlled environment, for instance through business simulation or role playing (Ahmad et al, 2004).

It seems that most authors categorize teaching methods into two groups, which are termed “traditional methods” (comprising normal lectures) and “innovative methods” (which are more action-based), also known as “passive methods” and “active methods”, respectively (Mwasalwiba, 2010).

Compared with passive methods, active methods according to Bennett (2006) are those that require the instructor to facilitate learning, not to control and apply methods that enable students' self-discovery. The three most used methods are: lectures, case studies, group discussions. These are actually the same methods used in other business-related courses, which according to Bennett (2006) are passive and less effective in influencing entrepreneurial attributes. Fiet (2000) explains that instructors rely on lecture-based methods because they can be easily accomplished, and also because they require less investment. Other methods used, but not as common as the previous group, include: business/computer or game simulations, video and filming, role models or guest speakers, business plan creation, project works. Also used were games and competitions, setting of real small business ventures, workshops, presentations and study visits. This latter category of methods is termed “active” and is said to be more appropriate for nurturing entrepreneurial attributes among participants (Mwasalwiba, 2010).

It is however also generally agreed that traditional methods are less effective in encouraging entrepreneurial attributes. It is said that such methods actually make students become dormant participants. These methods prepare a student to work for an entrepreneur, but not to become one. The existing shortfall in teaching methods confirms Kirby's (2004) comments that most entrepreneurship educators though relate their courses with new ventures creation (educate **for**), they actually end up teaching about entrepreneurship. If entrepreneurship is to be learned as a career, it is best done using some kind of apprenticeship. Traditional methods should only be used to give students the commercial underpinnings of their entrepreneurial actions. But, doing something practical and having an opportunity to question, investigate, converse, and discuss with real-world entrepreneurs gives both knowledge and skills and also stimulates attitudes. However, in a practical sense most of the advocated active/action-based teaching methods are costly and somehow may not align to the conventional university system of teaching and awarding (Mwasalwiba et al, 2010).

The teachers' main tasks are to provide theoretical knowledge on entrepreneurship and business planning, to instruct the students to find and test business ideas, and assess business opportunities and to consult group work and business plan writing. The students should realize the importance of preparing a business plan, gain an overview of the Business Plan structure and preparation process, and get some practice in writing a business plan on the basis of their own business idea. Knowledge on how to implement a business idea, experience of business planning and information on the process of setting up an enterprise should motivate students to think about setting up their own business and as a result, bring more of them to entrepreneurship (Venesaar, 2008).

Business Plan Development Instructional Strategy

One of the more popular curricula formats consists of teaching and monitoring the production of a business plan. In a study of leading entrepreneurship educators, the development of a business plan is identified as being the most important course feature of entrepreneurship courses (Honig, 2004).

A business plan may be defined as a written document that describes the current state and the presupposed future of an organization (Honig, 2004; White et al, 2010). Preparing a business plan produces an aura of formality and conviction often required before an individual's creation of a new venture will be taken seriously. Business planning is meant to be the first step toward a specific process widely known as entrepreneurship, but unlike the activity of entrepreneurship, it focuses primarily on ideas as opposed to actions (Honig, 2004). A well-crafted business plan is

one of the most important communication tools for an entrepreneur and provides a sense of legitimacy to the firm and the founders. The lack of a good business plan may be perceived as a lack of intent or commitment on the part of the founder(s). Many entrepreneurs discover that the preparation of a well-crafted business plan can be a daunting task. A well-written plan is concise, yet comprehensive and requires a myriad of decisions about all aspects of new venture creation, from exploiting the opportunity to garnering resources and building the top management team.

Constructing a convincing business plan requires a deep understanding of the product, the competitive landscape, the business model, and the prospective financial model. However, understanding the business is not enough: a business plan must also be persuasive (White et al, 2010).

In considering entrepreneurship education, the pedagogical implications of business plans are paramount and should be of concern to many educators in the field (Honig, 2004). White et al (2010) suggests that an effective method for teaching skills associated with writing a business plan may be achieved through a process of translating academic research into pedagogy that may be useful in the classroom. Moreover, they suggest that in the particular case of teaching skills associated with understanding essential criteria of a business plan, the appropriate pedagogies are

similar to those used to teach a craft. A craft is commonly defined as an art, trade, or occupation requiring special skills.

Developing business plans is another key aspect of experiential learning in technopreneurship education. Students are often required to create comprehensive business plans for technology-based ventures, which involves researching market opportunities,

analyzing competition, and devising strategies for product development and commercialization. This process helps students understand the intricacies of launching and managing a technology startup, including financial planning, marketing strategies, and operational considerations. By developing and presenting business plans, students learn to articulate their ideas, assess the feasibility of their ventures, and refine their strategic thinking.

Experiential Learning in Technopreneurship Education

Experiential learning is a cornerstone of technopreneurship education, providing students with practical, hands-on experiences that bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world application (Albet et al, 2013) This approach is particularly effective in fostering an entrepreneurial mindset and equipping students with the skills necessary to navigate the complexities of technology-driven business ventures. By engaging in experiential learning,

students gain valuable insights into the entrepreneurial process and develop the capabilities required to succeed in dynamic, technology-focused environments

Industry Collaborations and Internships Instructional Strategy

Collaborations with industry partners and internships are integral components of experiential learning in technopreneurship programs. By working directly with technology companies, startups, and industry experts, students gain exposure to current industry practices, trends, and challenges (Dada, 2021). These collaborations often involve project-based work where students contribute to real-world initiatives, providing them with practical experience and networking opportunities. Internships further enhance this experience by allowing students to apply their skills in a professional setting, interact with industry professionals, and gain insights into the day-to-day operations of technology ventures. Experiential learning also emphasizes real-world problem-solving, where students tackle actual challenges faced by technology companies and entrepreneurs. This might involve working on projects related to technology innovation, market entry strategies, or operational improvements (Lajin, 2023). By addressing these challenges, students gain practical insights into the complexities of technology entrepreneurship and develop problem-solving skills that are essential for success in the field. This approach encourages critical thinking, creativity, and the application of theoretical knowledge to practical situations.

An essential component of experiential learning is the opportunity for feedback and reflection. Students receive feedback from instructors, industry mentors, and peers on their projects, simulations, and business plans. This feedback helps them understand their strengths and areas for improvement, and reflection allows them to evaluate their experiences and learning outcomes. Through this iterative process, students refine their skills, adapt their approaches, and enhance their overall understanding of industrial collaboration.

Developing an entrepreneurial mindset is a fundamental goal of industrial collaboration education, as it equips students with the attitudes, skills, and behaviors necessary to succeed in technology-driven ventures. This mindset encompasses attributes such as resilience, adaptability, creativity, and proactive problem-solving, which are crucial for navigating the dynamic and often uncertain landscape of entrepreneurship. Industrial collaboration education integrates various strategies to cultivate this mindset, preparing students to lead innovative technology initiatives and drive business success.

Theoretical Review

The current study was guided by Social Learning Theory (SLT). It is also referred to as Social Cognitive Theory (SCT). The theory was pioneered by Herbert Bandura whose work began in the 1960s. The theory has been used in various studies related to students' learning including the area of entrepreneurship. The study by Byrne & Toutain (2012) found that 60.8% of 97 reviewed articles were connected to SCT as compared to other famous learning theories such as behaviorism, humanism and constructivism. The main assumption of the SLT is that people learn through observation, imitation, and modeling when there are interactions with other people in the social context. By observing others, people acquire skills, rules, strategies, attitudes, and beliefs. Also, people learn how to appropriately use learned modeled behaviour. Bandura (1994) came up with the concept of self-efficacy which is referred to an individual's personal belief of his or her capacity to accomplish the task. According to Bandura (1994), self-efficacy results from the mastery of experiences, social persuasion, social modeling and psychological responses. Bandura (1994) argues that the higher the self-efficacy the higher the possibility of accomplishing the task while the lower the self-efficacy the lower the possibility of accomplishing the task.

Regarding the current study as far as EE is concerned, instructors and other people in the social context should be role models and mentors to students (Marquardt & Waddill, 2004). In order to learn EE effectively and become successful entrepreneurs, students are required to observe and imitate the activities of successful entrepreneurs. The involvement of successful graduate entrepreneurs is of great importance to re-shape existing teaching methods and assessment of EE in HLE. Besides suggesting how teaching methods and assessment procedures should be improved, successful graduate entrepreneurs are role models to other graduates who have failed to start-up their own business ventures due to various reasons because they are in the field of entrepreneurship. The theory of SCT is relevant to the current study because it will help in exploring about what successful graduate entrepreneurs define EE and how it can be taught for self-employment among the graduate of HLE in Nigeria. In addition, successful

graduate entrepreneurs as role models in society can address various challenges encountering graduates to start-up their own business ventures. Furthermore, it is within the basis of the selected theory in which the findings of the study will be discussed in comparison to the underlying theoretical stances.

Empirical Review

In India, Pradhan & Sahoo (2013) assessed the challenges of EE in India. Firstly, it was observed that EE is not holistically taught in India since it focuses much on education-related to business management or general business. Being the case, some important skills such as leadership, creative thinking, exposure to technology and innovation are little emphasized. Secondly, it was observed that most of the teaching approaches and assessment are traditional oriented. Therefore, the study recommended that there should be improvements in teaching methods and assessment procedures to make EE more effective.

In South Africa, Radipere (2012) examined the state of EE and how it was taught in South African universities. The study found that the intended objective of EE is not met since many of the entrepreneurial graduates seek jobs due to the weaknesses of teaching methods characterized by traditional approaches of teaching (teacher-centered) rather than learner-centered. The study recommended that EE should adapt interactive methods of teaching such as simulation that allows students to practice what they learn theoretically. However, despite the good recommendation made by Radipere (2012) on improving methods of teaching EE, yet the study did not include contributions of successful graduate entrepreneurs in improving methods for EE teaching.

Methodology

Research Design of the Study

This study adopted simple survey research design. The area of study is Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana. Afikpo Local Government of Ebonyi State. The data for this study is primary sourced through the use of questionnaire. The population of the study comprised (700) lecturers, skill facilitators and students in Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana. Afikpo Local Government Area of Ebonyi State.

Sample Size Determination

The Cochran formula was adopted in determination of the sample size of the study. Cochran formula allows a researcher to calculate an ideal sample size given a desired level of precision, desired confidence level, and estimated proportion of the attribute present in the population. The target population from which we randomly selected our sample was considered 700. We assumed that the confidence interval of 10% and confidence level of 95%. The sample size actually obtained for this study was 248.

Instrument of Data Collection

The research instrument that was used by the researcher in collecting useful information on this topic is the questionnaire administration.

In this study, the questionnaire used by the researcher was properly structured and contained close ended questions to elicit relevant reactions from the respondents. It was carefully designed to accommodate two sections. The first section is the personal data which was used to generate proper data regarding the respondents' characteristics like, sex, age, and marital status while the second section dealt on relevant aspects of the topic under study. A five-point Likert scale was used to design the questionnaire which was used to generate data needed for the study.

Validation of the Instrument

To ensure validity of the research questionnaires the set of drafted questions was sent to an expert in the related field, who ensured that the questions were clearly appropriate and covered the research objectives of the study.

After this a pilot study of two of the respondents was carried out to test the effectiveness of the instrument of data collection. This was done by administering the questionnaire to them and ascertains how they responded to them.

The combined effort led to modification of some questions, additions, and selection of some other leading to a set of questions that are clear, unambiguous with enough coverage of the research objectives.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was ascertained with Cronbach's alpha which is measure of internal consistency that is how closely related a set of items are as a group. It is considered to be a measure of scale reliability. The Cronbach's scale must be up to 0.7 and above for an instrument to be declared reliable. The Cronbach's alpha obtained from the scaled reliability test was 0.75 showing that the instrument was reliable.

Model Specification

The following model was developed based on the variables used in the study:

$$R = (X_1, Y_1), (X_2, Y_2) \dots\dots\dots (X_n, Y_n)$$

$$R = (D_1, BPIS_1), (D_2, ICIS_2), \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where:

R = Coefficient of Determination

D = Improved teaching of entrepreneurship development education

BPIS = Business plan development instructional strategy

ICIS = Industrial collaboration instructional strategy

Method of Data Analysis

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to test the relationship between the independent and the dependent variables whereby business plan development instructional strategy, and industrial collaboration instructional strategy will be used as proxy for innovative strategies (independent variables) while improved teaching of entrepreneurship development education is the dependent variable. This test will be done at 5% significant level, which means the higher correlation coefficient; the association level was stronger between the two variables. The correlation coefficient can be either positive or negative, is depending on the direction of the relationship between the two variables

Data Presentation and Analyses

Test of Hypotheses

A hypothesis is a predicted answer to a research question. It is an a priori statement about the likely outcome of a research effort. This supposition based on what others have done. Two hypotheses were altogether postulated for this study. This section is dedicated to testing of these hypotheses.

As stated earlier, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to measure the strength of the association between the variables used. Two Pearson correlation test were employed to assess predictive validity of the posited variable.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

Restatement of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between business plan development instructional strategy and improved teaching of entrepreneurship development education.

H_{i1}: There is significant relationship between business plan development instructional strategy and improved teaching of entrepreneurship development education.

Table 1: Showing the correlation result output of how business plan development instructional strategy will result to improved teaching of entrepreneurship development education.

		<i>Improved teaching of entrepreneurship education</i>	<i>Business plan development instruction strategy</i>
<i>Business plan development instruction strategy</i>	Pearson Correlation	1	.723**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	360	360
<i>Improved teaching of entrepreneurship education</i>	Pearson Correlation	.723**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	240	240

Source: SPSS 25 Output

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the correlation table 1, the correlation value of 72.3% is a relationship that is very strong. The p-value of the variable is greater than the level of significance of 5% (0.00 > 0.01). This shows that there is positive and strong correlation between business plan development instructional strategy and improved teaching of entrepreneurship development education, which is also significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). This means that we uphold the alternate hypothesis. This implies that business plan development instructional strategy does significantly relate with and improved teaching of entrepreneurship development education in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Restatement of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between industrial collaboration instructional strategy and industrial collaboration instructional strategy.

H_{i2}: There is significant relationship between industrial collaboration instructional strategy and improved teaching of entrepreneurship development education.

Table 2: Showing the correlation result output of how instructional industrial collaboration instructional strategy will result to improved teaching of entrepreneurship development education.

		<i>Improved teaching of entrepreneurship education</i>	<i>industrial collaboration instructional strategy</i>
<i>industrial collaboration instructional strategy</i>	Pearson Correlation	1	.967**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	360	360
<i>Improved teaching of entrepreneurship education</i>	Pearson Correlation	.967**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	240	240

Source: SPSS 25 Output.

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the correlation table 4.1.8, the correlation value of 96.7% is a relationship that is very strong. The p-value of the variable is greater than the level of significance of 5% ($0.00 > 0.01$). This shows that there is positive and strong correlation between industrial collaboration instructional strategy and improved teaching of entrepreneurship development education, which is also significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). This means that we uphold the alternate hypothesis. This implies that industrial collaboration instructional strategy does significantly relate with improved teaching of entrepreneurship development education in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

Summary of Findings

The following findings were made from the study.

- i. The findings showed that business plan development instructional strategy can positively and significantly improve teaching of entrepreneurship development education in the Nigeria tertiary institutions. This implies that business plan development instructional strategy has a positive influence on the teaching of entrepreneurship development education in the Nigeria tertiary institutions under study.
- ii. It was discovered from the study that industrial collaboration instructional strategy positively and significantly relates to the teaching of entrepreneurship development education in the Nigeria tertiary institutions. This implies that industrial collaboration instructional strategy has a positive influence on the teaching of entrepreneurship development education in the Nigeria tertiary institutions.

Conclusion

In the light of the findings, the discussions and the summary, we hereby conclude that both business plan development instructional strategy and industrial collaboration instructional strategy positively and strongly relate with the teaching of entrepreneurship development education in the Nigeria tertiary institutions. We therefore conclude that business plan development instructional strategy and industrial collaboration instructional strategy can enhance the teaching of entrepreneurship development education in the Nigeria tertiary institutions. This is in line with the statement of (Honig, 2004), that the pedagogical implications of business plans are paramount and should be of concern to many educators in the field.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, discussions and conclusion of this study, we hereby recommend as follows:

- I. In the light of positive and significant relationship between business plan development instructional strategy and the teaching of entrepreneurship development education in the Nigeria tertiary institutions. This study hereby recommends that the tertiary institutions in Nigeria should adopt more of business plan development instructional strategy because it contains the appropriate pedagogies which are similar to those used to teach a craft. A craft is commonly defined as an art, trade, or occupation requiring special skill.
- II. Finally, since industrial collaboration instructional strategy positively and significantly relates to the teaching of entrepreneurship development education in the Nigeria tertiary institutions. Nigeria tertiary institutions should increase their industrial collaboration instructional strategy as an effective method of teaching of entrepreneurship development education Internships further enhance this experience by allowing students to apply their skills in a professional setting, interact with industry professionals, and gain insights into the day-to-day operations of technology ventures. Experiential learning also emphasizes real-world problem-solving, where students tackle actual challenges faced by technology companies and entrepreneurs.

Contribution to Knowledge

- i. This study has contributed to knowledge by highlighting that business plan development instructional strategy enhances the teaching of entrepreneurship development education in the Nigeria tertiary institutions.
- ii. This study has equally contributed to knowledge by indicating that industrial collaboration instructional strategy positively enhances the teaching of entrepreneurship development education in the Nigeria tertiary institutions.

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